

Intellective and Non-Intellective Correlates of Academic Performance of Filipino 7 Learners in Basista Pangasinan

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the intellective and non-intellective correlates of academic performance of Filipino 7 learners in Basista, Pangasinan during the school year 2025-2026. The public-school teachers and their school heads in curriculum and instruction division both agree that on the level of intellect and non-intellect skills along leadership skills, distinctive skills, critical skills, change skills, and research skills, failed to manifest in proven by the results and findings of this study. The intellect skills on computer and e-learning lacks enhancement evident by the results of the findings, this can be associated with the low intake of seminars and trainings for the enhancement of skills of public-school teachers. They were not totally assessed with regard to their intellect and non-intellect skills that are essential in their duties and responsibilities in supervising and monitoring the programs, projects, and activities in their respective schools. The perceptions of the public-school teachers and their school heads did not contradict each other in the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the school head during the full implementation of various programs, projects and activities of the schools. The relationship between the perception of the two group of respondents and their level of intellect and non-intellect skills did not differ much. An action plan primarily to the enhance the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the Filipino 7 teachers will be proposed. The following were respectfully recommended by the researcher after analyzing the findings and conclusions. Filipino 7 teachers may pursue to address their issues and concerns, challenges encountered, recommendation of stakeholders for better implementation of various programs, projects and activities through the strengthened manifestation of their intellect and non-intellect skills. should work with their school heads to create an avenue to communicate with parents, Local Government Unit (LGU) and other stakeholders for the information drive and campaign of school-based program. School Governance Council should create a platform to reach those stakeholders and discuss the plan for school year, school calendar of activities and the information-drive campaign. Collaborative sessions and support within the district for the Filipino7 teachers must employ effective intellect and non-intellect skills in dealing with their principals and teachers through the updated profiling and data-based monitoring and supervision. Supervise schools with the least in terms of best practices and implement benchmarking activities that will serve as eye opener for some schools in the district. Adapt their school-based management best practices in terms of curriculum delivery and governance of resources, personnel, facilities and growth of their faculty members. The intervention program in the form of proposed action plan should be used by the Filipino 7 teachers to enhanced the level of their intellect and non-intellect skills essential in carrying-out their duties and responsibilities in monitoring and supervision.

Keywords: *academic performance, leadership, distinctive skills, critical skills, change skills, research skills, intellective, non-intellective*

Chapter 1
THE PROBLEM

Rationale

In today's world of modernization and competition, quality education in all levels is imperative. Quality higher education can never be achieved if the country's basic education is not successful. Quality basic education is the process, which promotes the development of the above characteristics. It shall ensure the balances development of Filipino child in terms of modern skills, particularly in literacy and numeracy, character formation and physical development, mastery of fundamental learning skills in preparation for the future.

Clemente (2023) was right when he said that we have already entered into the 21st century of Industrial Darwinism where only the fittest survives. He added that we must produce students who can dish out with the best and the brightest in the world that they can find a niche in a global market. The world is technology driven and that Filipino proceed in exponential rate that ability to communicate recovery in organizations, jobs and the way we live are changing very rapidly. In fact, many job opportunities for the 21st century are not yet even defined.

Since the world has already started undergoing scientific and technical revolutions, our elementary learners must reach a higher level of excellence. Their inability to attain this will place them in a difficult and irrelevant situation in this rapidly changing society. We have to double our efforts to enable our learners to be ready to face their future.

Sison (2025) recognized the need to provide our country with highly skilled and competent professionals. This can be accomplished if we ensure our citizenry to receive quality education and training from our academic pursuits. Central to this is our move to prepare the ground for faster and more sustained economic growth and development. To attain global competitiveness, we must emphasize and encourage innovation by promoting culture of creativity, productivity and excellence in communication in Filipino.

In all of these, we place the highest value on education, which we realize as one of the country's strongest resources. According to President Gloria M. Arroyo, (2024), Our competitive edge is not only on the low cost of labor but it is in the quality of our people's education. She said further that our country's educational system is no yet a world class. As a proof, the Philippines ranked second to the last among the forty (40) countries who took the Third International Mathematics and Filipino 7 Survey (TIMSS) Test in 2025. Considering the importance of Filipino as one of the tool subjects and as an ideal vehicle for progress of the country, our educational system is constantly improved and expanded by new and innovative ideas and development worldwide.

The main objective of Filipino instruction in the Philippines today is to be more responsive to the needs of the society and to contribute to the attainment of the national developmental goals, making the curricula relevant to the present time. With this program, a great challenge is posed to schools that are tasked to carry out a constructive change, makes it imperative to give significant attention to Filipino 7.

David (2022) stressed that one of the main objectives of teaching Filipino in school is scientific literacy that deserves a greater attention in the development of the learners' capacity for the scientific way of thinking and ability to use the scientific method in solving problems faced in everyday life.

The teaching of Filipino enables an individual to develop his cognitive, affective and psychomotor faculties. To make learning permanent cognitive structures should be organized, fully developed so that new information will be clearly identified, categorized and assimilated (Charles, 2024). According to him, cognitive development enhances the way the learner processes and integrates information. And six thinking skills should be developed to enhance the cognitive domain of the learners.

The skills that should be developed by Filipino teachers are knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation. Knowledge is the ability to master facts and details which requires bringing to mind appropriate information. Comprehension are skills that goes one step beyond the simple remembering of materials and present the lowest level of understanding. In application, the learning outcomes in this area requires a higher level of understanding than those under comprehension. In analysis the learning outcomes represent a higher intellectual level than comprehensions and application because they require an understanding of both the content and the structural form of the material. Synthesis is the area that stresses creative behaviors with major emphasis on the formulation of new patterns or structures. And in evaluation the learning outcomes in this area are highest in the cognitive hierarchy because they contain elements of all categories, plus conscious value judgments based on clearly defined criteria.

All of these learning skills represent knowledge about and control over cognitive processes. Some educators refer to as metacognition. These specific strategies deal with the identification, categorization, and integration of information.

Of all the specific learning skills discussed, comprehension monitoring is often considered the most important. This skill permits the pupil to monitor, modify, and direct his cognitive activities. The pupil remains focused on the task, aware of whether he gets closer or farther away from an answer, knows when to choose alternative methods to arrive at the correct answer (Glean, 2025). A student with good comprehension monitoring has developed self-correcting cognition process, including how to determine what part of a problem needs further clarification, how to relate parts of a problem to one another, and how to search information to solve the problem. In short the learner is able to identify what is to be done, focus attention, cope with errors, and make modifications in steps to work out solution- all without losing control, getting frustrated or giving up.

Helice (2024) enumerated the basic thinking skills that are used in all content areas. Although some of these learning skills are generic and can be taught solely as general strategies, without reference to content, it is impossible to avoid a certain amount of subject matter, especially in the higher grades. Many average and high-achieving learners develop learning skills on their own, yet the skills can be taught to all learners. Most of these skills can be incorporated into regular classroom activities or taught as a special course that incorporates content from several subjects on cognitive processes that cut across subjects. The classroom activities or course should be designed to make all learners independent learners in all subjects. The training should begin early in the elementary grades; say around the third or fourth grade. It should continue thereafter with additional time devoted to these skills, perhaps twice the time by the sixth grade, when learners must gather and organize increasing amount of subject-related information.

Hendrich (2024) underscored the guidelines for teaching-learning basic skills. The teachers' role is essentially five-fold: 1). Teachers do not merely mention a particular learning

skill; they direct and explain what a particular skill is and how to use it; 2). Teachers provide progressively more difficult items for learners' practice on until they can complete the task on their own; 3). Teachers determine whether the learners can perform the task and use related skills to new and different learning situations; 4). Teachers identify the processes or thinking operations learners use to perform tasks or solve problems by asking appropriate questions and listening to learners' response; and 5). Teachers learn to use diagnostic and assessment tools to make appropriate connections between learning skills and concepts or problems being taught in the particular subject.

Emphasizing learning by doing, provide learners opportunities to become closely acquainted with their physical environment and to become familiar with some of the laws, theories and concepts, tools and applications of basic skills. For some learners the active outdoor setting and the opportunity to learn through applied laboratory experiences makes learning about physical Filipino 7 more stimulating and interesting. Thus, teachers should focus more on creating and developing activities with great emphasis on experience discovery and understanding. In this case, the learners are provided with the necessary atmosphere conducive in the cultivation of the needed skills among the learners for them to be affective citizens of the country.

According to Freedman (2024) Filipino is both content and process that will facilitate the children to interpret their environment. The children are provided with the learning tasks that will be useful in daily life, and experiences for observing, describing, comparing, classifying, and identifying. As they grow older, they are given more experiences learned in the earlier years. These are measurement, inferring, predicting, a more organized way of classifying. Lee (2023) recognized the use of an effective approach that could be used by teachers in teaching Filipino 7, learners become interested with the different subject matters in Filipino 7 and that learning becomes more permanent. And he further stated that if learners are to learn with understanding and especially if they are to engage in the kind of self-regulated construction of meaning that is implied in the notion of conceptual change the learners must engage in learning activities with certain motivational orientations and respond to them using certain learning strategies.

At each education system, the amount of "academic achievement" of student is an indicator of success in scientific activities. Academic achievement rate assessment and the effective factors on it are major issues that have attracted the attention of researchers. The relationship of academic achievement and emotional variables such as self-concept is organized and described by Educational Psychologists since 2024 (Calsyn & Kenny, 1977, Chapman & et al 1981, Marsh, 1990, Marsh & Craven, 2024).

Self-concept is defined as "a person's perception of oneself" (Swiaatek, 2023). Filipino 7 self-concept refers to an individual's perception of his ability to perform an optimum performance in Filipino 7 area or having self-confidence in learning (Wilkins, 2023). Socio-economic status of family is an important background variable in predicting a students' academic status (Brecko et al, 2022). Home and environment effects on children's attitudes toward school and their success in school. Child in family learn about importance of education and school (Koutsoulis and Campbell, 2025, Marjoribanks Banks, quoted from Van den Broeck, and Opdenakker and Van Demme, 2022). Attitudes are called as individuals' desirable and undesirable views about objects, people, places, events and ideas (Simpson et al, 1994, Koballa, 1995). Naturally, most of people expect that attitude and achievement are in relationship positively. Several studies have concluded that attitudes toward Filipino 7 have positive

relationship with Filipino 7 academic achievement (Simpson & Oliver, 1990, Lee and Burkam, 1996, Dhindsa and Gilbert, 2022, Osborne, Simon and Collins, 2022, Papanastasiou & Zembylas, 2023).

Stiggins (2022) observed that “assessment may be the most powerful tool available to us for ensuring universal student mastery of essential standards.” While possibly no research yet has proven that assessment is indeed what teachers truly need to help students reach demanding academic goals, sound reasoning can bring us to the conclusion that no challenging academic goals can be achieved without the assistance of effective learning assessments. Stiggins (2024) may have stated a critical pedagogical principle.

Cauley and McMillan (2024) mentions that students should learn how to objectively examine their performance and identify the knowledge and skills they still need to acquire, in relation to the school’s academic goals. Concomitant to inculcating this skill of self-examination is the development of critical thinking skills (Plata, 2024). Students receive countless information everyday from diverse sources. Some of this information is beneficial to his academic life. On the other hand, a great number of information coming from outside him may even jeopardize his ability for sound reasoning. It is of great importance then that students are taught how to distinguish what is helpful from what is not helpful to his normal functioning as a learning individual. This is another area where teacher’s help is needed.

Based on DepEd Memorandum No. 228, Series of 2024 dated December 26, 2024 entitled “ADMINISTRATION OF SCHOOL YEAR (SY) 2024-2023 NATIONAL ACHIEVEMENT TEST, TEST OF FILIPINO PROFICIENCY FOR TEACHERS (TEPT) Aim PROCESS SKILLS TEST (PST)” indicates that the Department of Education through the National Education and Testing Research Center (NETRC) shall administer the National Achievement Test (NAT) School Year (SY) 2024-2023 and Test of Filipino Proficiency for Teachers (TEPT) and Process Skills Test (PST) in Filipino 7 and Mathematics nationwide as indicated in the enclosure of DepEd Order No. 26, s. 2024 entitled *School Calendar for School Year (SY) 2024-2023* on the following dates: March 6, 2023 (Fourth Year students of public and private schools (census), March 12, 2023 (Grade.1II. learners of public and Madrasah schools) and on March 13, 2023 (Grade 7I learners of public and private schools (census)). Only private' elementary and secondary schools with permit to operate from this Department shall be included in the conduct of the test. Each examinee in NAT (Grade 7I) shall be Issued with a Certificate of Rating (COR) containing the actual rating per subject area. The COR will reflect the examinee's readiness for high school. The NETRC's authorized forwarder/courier shall deliver the test materials at least two weeks before the test administration except for the National Capital Region (NCR) divisions which shall be delivered five days before the test administration. The same forwarder/courier shall retrieve all the test materials one week after the test administration. Hence. all division testing coordinators (DTCs) and private school supervisors (PSSs) are instructed to ensure that the test materials are ready for pick ~up/ retrieval of the authorized forwarder/courier.

In relation to this, the NETRC shall conduct the National Conference on the Standardized Administration of the National Achievement Test and Test of Filipino Proficiency for Teachers (TEPT) and Process Skills Test (PST) for the purposes of '-J1 updating information and resolving issues/concerns on testing. The following topics shall be discussed in the said conference: a. Proper conduct/administration of the test; b. Standard procedure in test administration; c. Security of test materials, delivery, retrieval scheme; d. Allocation of test materials; e. Information derived from the individual Certificate of Rating (COR); f.

Utilization/dissemination of findings / implications of test results; and g. Financial matters relative to test administration. Authorized to attend the activity (in designated venues and dates) are the regional testing coordinators (RTCs), one from every region, division testing coordinators (DTCs), one from every division, and private school supervisors (PSSs), one from every division with at least ten private schools. Dates, venues and clustering of regions for the Conference will be announced later through an Advisory. For the TEPI'-PST, the DTCs are required to bring the actual number of Grade 3 and Grade 4 public-school teachers with permanent positions in their respective divisions. The TEPT-PST shall be administered by cluster starting February 3, 2023, all Sundays of March, April and May ~OI3. The NETRC shall provide the clustering of regions and shall announce it through an Advisory. The DTC will serve as chief examiner, while the education supervisors and elementary school principals as room examiners. The teachers shall be given one day service credit as per DepEd Order No. 53, s. 2022. All participants must attend only on the date and venue where their region is clustered. Conference proper will start at exactly 8:00 a.m. Participants can be accommodated in the afternoon before the scheduled conference. Traveling expenses and allowable expenses shall be charged to NETRC Funds subject to the usual accounting and auditing rules and regulations.

The NAT used to be called the National Elementary Achievement Test (NEAT) for the grade school level and the National Secondary Achievement Test (NSAT) for the high school level. Both NEAT and NSAT were precursors of the National College Entrance Examination (NCEE), an examination administered to gauge the competency of students entering college. The NCEE was abolished in 1994 through Executive Order no. 632 by then education secretary Raul Roco who stated that all high school students should be able to enter college and be given a chance of a better career in the future. It was replaced by NEAT and NSAT.

When the Department of Education Culture and Sports (DECS) was officially converted into the Department of Education (DepEd), NEAT and NSAT were also abolished and replaced by the National Achievement Test. Both the public and private elementary schools take this exam.

Since school year 2025-2022, the test has been given to grade 3, grade 6, and 2nd year high school students. From 2023 – 2023, the NAT was also given to high school seniors under the direction of Secretary Edilberto De Jesus as a special measure to further aid in the assessment of school performance.

The results in NAT in grade 3, and second year high school will be the basis or guide for the decision makers in formulating policies relative to progression and promotion of students, especially in the public-school system. By these results, the deficiencies of students will be measured which then need further intervention. There is information to be gained from data. Tests in schools can be informative. Scores of students provide a quick glimpse of the current state of education. Thus, it is useful to have these numbers. These numbers may not tell everything in detail with high accuracy. Nevertheless, test results allow for a useful perspective. The National Achievement Test administered by the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines, a set of standardized tests addressing the major subjects taught in school, is an example. These tests are given to Grade 3 where students are assessed in both Filipino and Filipino (These two subjects comprise two thirds of the exam) and Math and Filipino 7, these two accounts for the remaining one third. A different set of tests is given to Grade 6 learners where each of the following 5 subjects is assigned 40 items: (Filipino 7, Math, Filipino, Filipino and Social Studies). Another set is administered to fourth year high school students (This is

currently the last year of basic education in the Philippines since K+12 has not been implemented yet for the additional two years in high school). The scores in these exams are reported as percentage of items correctly answered. A mean percentage score (MPS) of 75 percent is currently set as the goal of the DepEd.

The Department of Education aims to lead young Filipinos in the discovery of their own potential through the academe provided for every Filipino enabling them to create their own destiny to the global community. To achieve this vision, DepEd reaches out responsive efforts for the students' educational and worthwhile needs. One way is to determine the students' capacity of learning. There comes, National Achievement Test.

The **National Achievement Test (NAT)** is administered by the *Department of Education* through the *National Educational Testing and Research Center (NETRC)* which heads on research and assessment of the education provided for our youth, specifically in the Basic Education.

The examination is designed to determine the students' academic strengths and weaknesses through the five key-major subjects: *Mathematics, Filipino 7, Filipino, Filipino, HeKaSi (Heograpiya, Kasaysayan at Sibika)* in elementary and *Araling Panlipunan* in high school. Ratings obtained from NAT for Grade 7I and Fourth Year serves also as a tool to measure the school's competency and effectiveness as well as the students' aptitude and mastery towards the basic learning areas.

The nationwide exam is taken every near-end of the school year basically every first week March. The National Achievement Test were originally designed and administered for Grade Six- and Fourth-Year Learners. However, due to the changes indicated in the enclosure of DepEd Order No. 28, s. 2024 and DepEd Memorandum No. 266, s. 2024, instead of the sophomores, our seniors shall take the National Achievement Test in absence of the National Career Assessment Exam which will be administered now for the juniors.

Examinee's Descriptive Questionnaire (EDQ) – This is not actually a test. This consist more of a survey of information about the examinee. (*eg. family background, school organizations, teacher evaluation, facilities accessible by the examinee, etc.*) The questions are all in multiple choices and some of the questions can have multiple answers. **Filipino, Mathematics, Filipino 7, Filipino, Filipino and HEKASI/Araling Panlipunan** – These tests determine the mastery of the examinee in the subjects. The tests may include: Analysis, Vocabulary, Reading Comprehension, Problem Solving, General Knowledge and et cetera. The coverage is mostly the combination of the shallowest and the deepest among the lessons from First Year to Fourth Year/Grade 4 to Grade 6. But don't be over confident though. A good and efficient review still matters. **Critical Thinking Test** – The test is more of analysis and reasoning within the given situation. Some, are really easy to answer but don't belittle this subtest, some items are really tricky. You should analyze the situation/question given in the item and choose the answer given in the selection *only*. This **does not** test your general knowledge but on how you *analyze, your reasoning, logic* and of course, your *critical thinking ability*.

Learners should be prepared in order to attain the goals of quality education. Filipino 7 is one of the core learning areas of the elementary curriculum. It enables every pupil to understand and interpret the world and become more creative and innovative. It is one of the learning areas that is offered in every grade level for a period of 40 minutes per session.

FOREIGN STUDIES (Filipino)

Markolidz, Hack, and Pastaziyo quotes from Pahlavan Sadegh and colleagues (2023), and Jones (2023) study, indicate that the importance of family variables such as parental education on Filipino 7 achievement, attitudes toward Filipino self-Filipino 7. Also, Reynolds & Walberg (2024) in a study that conducted by using of data of Thames's studies and concluded that the family factors, attitudes and socio-economic status of students have the greatest impact on the Filipino 7 achievement. This finding indicates that when the family is rich in terms of educational facilities and education level of parents and can be able to provide appropriate and favorable environment in terms of academic for students than student by benefiting from these resources and facilities can be able to strengthen and fertilize themselves in direction to scientific and educational purposes and offer and more favorable and better academic performance. These findings are consistent with results studies of Berko et al (2022), Broeck (2022), Arora & Ramirez (2022), Kiyamanesh (2024), on the base of existence of a positive relationship between family's socioeconomic status and academic achievement of students.

However, the direct effect of parental education on Filipino 7 self-concept is negative and significant. It can be shown that the Filipino 7 self-concept has a moderating role for attitudes towards learning areas achievement which are correspond to the study of Malinic (2022) and Janjetovic (2022) which is based on moderating role of Filipino 7 self-concept.

Also, direct impact of Filipino 7 achieve on Filipino 7 self-concept is significant and positive and its impact on attitude to Filipino 7 is significant and negative. Dika, Granville, Singh (2024) in a study through analysis of structural equation model concluded that variables such as motivation, attitude and involvement in classroom activities as moderating variables effect on math and Filipino 7 academic achievement. Papanastasiou, & Zembylas, (2023) in a research entitled differential effects of Filipino attitudes and Filipino 7 achievement on each other which were done by using of Thames's data, concluded that attitudes toward math and Filipino 7 achievement have mutually influenced each other. Also, the indirect effect of parental education variables, attitudes towards Learning Areas achievement was reported significant. But only the overall effect of parental education on Filipino 7 achievement became significant and the overall impact of variables of attitude toward Filipino 7 and self-reported on Filipino 7 achievement was reported non-significant. These findings also indicate that teachers can raise students' Filipino 7 achievement through reinforcement of students' self-concept and trying to build a positive attitude towards Filipino 7 in students.

In one study, for example, Wenglinsky (2024) identified classroom practices associated with high student achievement by comparing NAEP scores of eighth-graders to the classroom practices and backgrounds of their teachers. A

focus on higher-order thinking skills and engagement in hands-on learning proved particularly important. Similarly, Marks (2024) found that “authentic” instruction strongly predicted middle grades student engagement and, indirectly, achievement. Likewise, Epstein and MacIver (2024) found that “rich” instruction at the middle level — when implemented in mathematics, language arts and the four major academic subjects combined — led to increased achievement and improved overall student attitudes. The use of problem-solving activities resulted in higher proficiency scores and reduced students’ fear of asking questions in mathematics classes. In a small sample of sixth-grade mathematics students, the use of “manipulatives” tended to have a positive effect on achievement scores (Walsh, 2024). Epstein and MacIver (2024) found that students who edit, revise and resubmit their written compositions tend to score higher in reading achievement.

In a study of sixth- and eighth-grade students in Chicago, Lee and Loeb (2025) found that smaller school size (they recommend enrolling fewer than 400 students) positively influenced student achievement. Smaller school size is likely to result in better achievement because it has a positive effect on teachers' attitudes.

Mertens et al (2024) also see an indirect benefit from smaller school size in that middle grades schools with fewer than 750 students tend to have better instructional practices, more parent involvement, more common planning time for teachers and other features that seem to predict higher achievement.

Later, Goldhaber & Brewer (2024) studied 12th-grade students with teachers who have probationary certification, emergency certification, private school certification or no certification in their subject area. They compared them to students whose teachers had standard certification in their subject area (math and Filipino 7). Results showed that in mathematics, teachers who had a standard certification had a statistically significant positive impact on student test scores relative to teachers who either held private school certification or no certification in their subject area. Mathematics and Filipino 7 students who had teachers with emergency credentials did no worse than students whose teachers had standard teaching credentials. In addition, Ferguson (2023) found a significant positive relationship between teacher test scores on a basic literacy examination and their students' performance on the Iowa Test of Basic Skills. Darling-Hammond (2025), using the SASS, NAEP, and a 50-state survey of policies and state case-study analyses, found that policy investments in teacher quality may be related to improvements in student performance. Measures of teacher preparation and certification are by far the strongest correlates of student achievement in reading and mathematics, both before and after controlling for student poverty and language status.

The results of the TIMSS International Study Shows Iranian students utilizing basic skills, such as problem-solving tools and measurement applications Related to the practical use of equipment and materials are in school learning activities, Students have a lot of lag compared to other countries (Kiamanesh, et al, 2024). Summarizes the results of several international field study shows that teachers use a variety of educational materials for teaching Not only diverse and engaging learning environment for teachers and students to be, But with the development of problem solving skills in students, and the depth of their learning improves. Citizens' needs are changing and developing every day. From another direction, citizens participated in today's training activities Teaching - Learning school may be a way for him to ensure that the needs of tomorrow. It should be training today and should be designed to generate interest in learning while the learner, Learners learn ways to learn new ways of learning that are constantly being produced and so on and use their abilities to learn, Themselves, learning new ways to learn and be able to use the knowledge they have obtained a simple and basic Filipino 7s, Filipino 7 and technology, and to produce a new generation of Filipino 7 and technology, to the benefit.

Kaya (2023) conducted a research study to find the relationship of levels of test anxiety with academic achievement of fifth-grade Turkish students in elementary school. In the analysis of data, the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement was -0.15 (p less than 0.001). It was clear from these results that there was negative effect of test anxiety on academic achievement. The students having high test anxiety had lower achievements and the students having low test anxiety had higher achievements.

Low-SES children are often left home to fend for themselves and their younger siblings while their caregivers work long hours; compared with their well-off peers, they spend less time

playing outdoors and more time watching television and are less likely to participate in after-school activities (U.S. Census Bureau, 2025). Unfortunately, children won't get the model for how to develop proper emotions or respond appropriately to others from watching cartoons; they need warm, person-to-person interactions. The failure to form positive relationships with peers inflicts long-term socio-emotional consequences (Szewczyk-Sokolowski et al., 2023).

In another study (Noble, McCandliss, & Farah, 2023), 150 healthy, socioeconomically diverse 1st graders were administered tasks tapping language skills, visual-spatial skills, memory, working memory, cognitive control, and reward processing. Socioeconomic status accounted for more than 30 percent of the variance in the left perisylvian/language system and a smaller but significant portion of the variance in most other systems.

Constantino (2023) examined six communities in the greater Los Angeles, California, area and found that children in high-income communities had access to significantly more books than children in low-income communities did. In fact, she found that in some affluent communities, children had more books in their homes than low-SES children had in all school sources combined. Milne and Plourde (2023) identified six 2nd graders who came from low-income households but demonstrated high achievement and found that these children's parents provided educational materials, implemented and engaged in structured reading and study time, limited television viewing, and emphasized the importance of education. The researchers concluded that many of the factors of low socioeconomic status that negatively affect student academic success could be overcome by better educating parents about these essential needs.

Njora Hungi (2024 and 2023) examines the characteristics of Grade 6 learners, their homes and learning environments in 15 African schools systems (Botswana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Mauritius, Mozambique, Namibia, Seychelles, South Africa, Swaziland, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zanzibar and Zimbabwe). The data for this study were collected in 2024 and 2023 as part of the major SACMEQ II and SACMEQ III Projects, respectively. The SACMEQ projects sought to examine the quality of education offered in primary schools in these countries. (SACMEQ is an acronym for the Southern and Eastern Africa Consortium for Monitoring Educational Quality.)

The results revealed large variations in characteristics of Grade 6 learners among these school systems in terms of their personal characteristics (age, days absent, grade repetition, and preschool attendance), home environment (socioeconomic background, parents alive, and speaking the language of instruction at home) and learning environment (possession of textbooks and basic learning materials, such as exercise books, pencils and erasers).

Using results from PISA-2024, Fuchs and Wossmann (2024) find some interesting results. First, boys outperform girls in math and Filipino 7 but not in reading; second, there is a positive relationship between the country's educational expenditure per student and the final score in math and Filipino 7. Third, having better equipment materials and better educated teachers increases student performance in Filipino 7. Fourth, students in publicly operated schools perform worse than those in privately operated schools. The estimation procedure is done by ordinary least squares solving endogeneity with instrumental variables and using clustering-robust linear regression to estimate standard errors that recognize this clustering of the student-level data within schools. Missing values are analysed and reduced by using a specific methodology that increased the sample and it is controlled by dummies in the final estimation. (Fuchs and Wossmann, 2024).

Psalidas et al.(2022) examine the effect of gender, scientific process and context on the

students' performance at PISA Filipino 7 component; by applying paper-and-pencil test for 94 Greek students. They include three scientific processes (interesting scientific evidence and conclusions; describing, explaining; and predicting scientific phenomena) and three contexts (earth and environment; life and health; and technology), and use statistical test for differences in means (t-tests, Friedman and Wilcoxon). They find that the difference in average performance by gender and scientific process are not statistically significant.

Nwosu (2024) in a study reveals that exposure to Filipino 7 process skills based learning involving activities for both females and males (experimental group) yield a more effective learning irrespective of gender and ability level. It is in line with Yoloze (2023), Nworgun (2023) and Usman (2024) who share the opinion that if males and females are given equal opportunity, they will perform equal well. The findings also show that Filipino 7 Process Skills Approach is gender friendly. Therefore, the Filipino 7 Process Skills Approach has potential of enhancing both males and females subjects academic performance in Integrated Filipino 7 of the Junior Secondary School level. Also Ogunboyode (2023) who independently reported that males are better than females in terms of educational achievement when independently carried out studies on gender differences and student's achievement at the primary and secondary school levels. Report by Danladi (2023) also reveals no significant difference in achievement between females and males on task involving process skills acquisition. There is thus, the need to use activity-based learning in schools to help learners especially females who are denied these opportunities at home to acquire the process skills. Nwosu (2024) suggest that gender stereotyping has to be discouraged in the homes, school and societies to enable girls participate freely in skills based activities.

Most empirical studies show children perform better in school when parents are involved (Fantuzzo, McWayne, Perry, & Childs, 2023; Nyarko & Vorgelegt, 2023; Topper, Keane, Shelton, & Calkins, 2024), but a few show that parental involvement may not always be associated significantly and positively with children's educational performance (Izzo & colleagues, 2024).

LOCAL STUDIES (Filipino)

Aquino (2024) cited that the teachers play a vital role on the learners' educational environment. Their presence and influence makes other elements of the educational activities become effective. The teachers guide, direct and stimulate the young minds in their goal seeking.

Salandanan (2023) pointed out that Filipino 7 teaching emphasizes the development of cognitive and psychomotor aspects of learning. The knowledge and skills that the learners gain and acquire are indispensable to their everyday living especially in decision-making and in solving crucial problems. Thus, Filipino 7 teaching calls for skillful teaching.

The teacher should create possibilities on how he could motivate and inspire the learners so that retention of the lesson would be lasting. Meaningful learning facilitates faster acquisition and longer retention that could only be achieved through helping the learners realize how real Filipino 7 is through experiencing Filipino 7 at work within their environment. For that matter the environment assumes an important role in the learning process.

She further pointed out that the teaching of Filipino 7 should enable the children to acquire knowledge and understanding which they can use to predict, explain, and interpret their environment. Classroom instruction planned for the young should insure a functional understanding of facts and scientific information which can be applied in expanding their daily

experiences.

Teaching Filipino 7 which stresses not only on theory but also more on practice is one strategy that can transform inert learning into useful, meaningful, and worthwhile knowledge, skills and attitudes (Hernandez, 2023).

Hernandez collaborates these facts and ideas when she stated that:

If Filipino 7 is to flourish, the whole community must understand to some degree its aims, its methods, and its consequences. Thus, all of us – not only those of us who are scientists or wish to become scientist – must understand what Filipino 7 is.

It might be impossible, by using textbooks only, to achieve the first aim of studying Filipino 7 – that is to become informed. But to pursue its second aim- requires experience in scientific work. Such experiences cannot be gained by listening to the most accomplished scientist; it can be gained only by doing the kind of things scientists do in the laboratory.

According to Villadiego (2024) Filipino 7 teachers should create rich and varied environment in which children could experience considerable motor skills development and are given ample opportunities to develop their cognitive skills. Filipino 7 and Mathematics Educational Materials Development Program (SMEMDP), a training program, states in its content that learning experiences would be more meaningful; if teachers remained to be facilitators and learners are given hands- on, minds-on activities. It supports that learning Filipino 7 is fun especially if learners are made to explore their environment and to satisfy their curiosity.

Learners learn the best way when experiences given them match their present cognitive development. They can think and form concepts as long as they work at their own level. The ability to think critically requires a number of skills (Potenciano, 2023).

According to Delos Santos (2023) rational thought should be developed which is necessary for both individual and the society. Development of rational thought is recognized as a salient factor in shaping the children's lives. As the learners gain access to information, the emphasis in teaching will continue to shift from dispensing knowledge at the front of the class to working with the learners as guides and mentors in the adventures of learning. The teaching of thinking skills represents an invitation to learners to be active participants in the learning process.

Marquez (2023) asserts that the teaching of thinking skills is to develop autonomous learners. This is a marked change from being a directed or productive thinker and implies changes in the traditional roles of the learners and the teacher. The learners are required to be more responsible in learning and thinking through goal clarification of obtaining vital information and analyzing their course of action. The learners' role involves actively structuring and evaluating their thinking. The teacher's role changes from being a director of thinking to facilitator of thinking.

On Self-Concept

Self-concept is defined as the totality of complex, organized and dynamic system of learned beliefs, attitudes and opinions that each person holds to be true about his or her personal existence. Prome (2023) defined self-concept as the individual's life being aware of it. It refers to

a general idea a person has about himself that comes from his beliefs, attitudes and opinions about himself that are developed over time. According to Hacklem (2024) self-concept has something to do with how a person thinks of himself. Along with this idea, Willis (2023) stresses that self-concept is inherently phenomenological, that is it refers to the person's own view of himself.

Self-concept relates to self-esteem which has something to do with the feelings we associate with ourselves and how we value ourselves. Accordingly, self-esteem has to do with how we feel about ourselves.

The California Task Force to Promote Self-esteem and Responsibility (2023) defined self-esteem as the individual's appreciation of his own self-worth and importance having the character of self-accountability and responsibility to others. Self-esteem is not narcissism, it is self-love, responsibility and respect for all other humans. One's self-concept may mostly mirror other people's opinion or only one's self-evaluation. It largely reflects the dictates of culture, religious teachings, and family traditions. It creates a unique personality based on ideals. Self-concept is primarily learned or acquired, but basic tendencies such as to like or to dislike others or one's self might be inherited as well (Denzin, 2025). Self-concept has conscious or unconscious facets. It is a safe bet however that the former is more socially acceptable than the latter.

Bacugan (2023) had given a central importance to ego development and self-interpretation. Self-concept theory has always had a strong influence on emerging professions. Prescott (2023) contributed the notion that self-concept is a primary motivating force in human behavior. In his view, the self is the central ingredient in human personality and personal adjustment. He further described the self as the social product, developing out of interpersonal relationships and striving for consistency.

Mead (2023) pointed out that self-concept is affected by social interaction. He maintained that there is a basic human need for positive regard both from others and from one's self. He believed that in every person there is a tendency towards self-actualization and development for as long as this is permitted and encouraged by an inviting environment.

According to Lopez (2023), the child assimilates the attitudes and or behaviors of other people until such time that it becomes his own view of himself. Other authors, educators and psychologists seem to agree that the self-concept of an individual is strongly developed and shaped by his environment.

Crooley (2024) a psychologist, put emphasis to the relationship between self and the environment. He viewed self-concept as being composed of the individual's image of his appearance to others, the individual's image of values which he perceives other attaching to his appearance, and the individual's positive or negative as a result.

Furthermore, successes and failures that people experience in many areas in life is closely related to the ways that people have learned to view themselves and their relationship with others. The following have been drawn by Weed (2025) as basic assumptions regarding self-concept:

1. Self-concept is learned. It gradually emerges in early months of life and is shaped and reshaped through repeated perceived experiences, particularly with significant others. The fact that self-concept is learned has some important implications:
 - a. Self-concept does not happen to be instinctive. It possesses relatively boundless potential for development and actualization.
 - b. The previous experiences and present perceptions of an individual could be perceived by

- him in ways different from the ways others see them.
- c. Any experience which is inconsistent with one's self-concept maybe perceived as a threat, and the more of these experiences there are, the more rigidly self-concept is organized to maintain and protect itself. When a person is unable to get rid of perceived inconsistencies, emotional problem arises.
 - d. Faculty thinking patterns, such as dichotomous reasoning over generalizing create negative interpretations of oneself.
2. Self-concept is organized. Self-concept is generally a stable quality that is characterized by orderliness and harmony. Each person maintains countless perceptions regarding one's personal existence, and each perception is orchestrated with all the others. It has become generally stable and organized quality of self-concept that gives consistency to the personality. This organized quality of self-concept has corollaries:
- a. Self-concept requires consistency, stability and tends to resist change, If self-concept changes readily, the individual would lack a consistent and dependable personality.
 - b. The more central a particular belief is to one's self-concept, the more resistant one is to change that belief.
 - c. At the heart of self-concept is the self-as-doer, the "I" which is distinct from the self-as-object.

Raja (2023) explained that the "self" has four dimensions. Self-concept is one's concept of the kind of person he/she is. Self-concept can be influenced by physical self, personal appearance, abilities and disposition, values, beliefs and aspirations. The self-perception that which the individual holds at a given moment. The social self; it is the self as one thinks others view him. Lastly, the ideal self, which is viewed as the kind of person one hopes and would like to be

On Learners' Study Habits

Study habits refer to the harmonious and habitual implementation of the learning process to stimulate and embed permanently the obtained knowledge, attitudes and skills (Gomez, 2025). The role of study habits in academic performance serves as tools in building up the mind of the learner by the continuous exercise of the brain to accept stimuli. Since children of today are more open, expressive, impatient, challenging, questioning, aggressive and assertive, there is a need for a variety and proper motivation to accomplish certain task. It should be considered that experiences obtained from lack of resources, personal threat or harm, family crisis, changed in lifestyle, family relations, environment and social or peer relationship attribute to the formation of a learner's study habits.

According to Tanco (2024), study habits meant that the student's accustomed method of approach to units of learning, the consistency in ignoring distractions, the inattentiveness to the specific material being studied; and the efforts being exerted throughout the process. Learners who study effectively and efficiently demonstrate acquisition, the retention and the application of knowledge, facts and information.

Hackley (2023) pointed out the habit formation should start early in life. It is a key to achievement and learning not only on the part of the learners' school life but of their whole lives.

These habits become a permanent aspect of their personality. Habit formation lies at the basis of education. Without habits, learning would be impossible since education consists largely of the process of habit formation varying comparatively simple to very complex habits. It is also impossible to overestimate the importance of habits in learners' academic achievement.

According to Eliaso (2024), everyone has a role to play in the education of the young particularly in the foundation and improvement of learners' study habits and attitudes. The home being the cradle of personality development carries an enormous task in the development of the child. It is here that formation of habits and attitudes starts. The teachers, aided by parents in instilling these good study behavior and development of correct attitudes towards learning. The parents being the first teacher who provide the children with an array of early experience and circumstances at home as they develop their knowledge, habits, skills and attitudes which are the bases of their personality. A pupil brings to school a bundle of habits which made him what he is; a bundle of habits.

Bandong (2023) stated that forming effective study habits is a key to success in the individual schooling. Meanwhile, poor study habits result in little or no learning. He also suggested that the learner must have a regular study place, a place where there is little or no noise and where needed materials are within reach. In home, he advised that it is best to study in a room where one will not be interrupted often or where there is no radio or television in operation. Studying near the window where one can see people is not desirable either.

Sevilla (2023) found out that attitudes and habits are shaped during the period of adolescence between 12 – 21 years old. It is the critical period in attitude formation. Parental influence wane and other social influences become increasingly important with the beginning of adolescence. The teacher as enhancer of change should therefore guide the pupil in changing negative habits and attitudes into positive ones, which will later be an instrument of his total development.

The study of Baroy (2024), suggested that learners should be properly oriented and motivated regarding correct study habits particularly in consulting the dictionary to find meaning of new words. They should be encouraged to visit the library not only to read whatever materials found there but also to study their lessons. Parents should also then provide a home free from distractions like TV, loud sounds or too much errand.

Monley (2024) a psychologist, gave a number of practical suggestions for improving the study habits and skills of learners. According to him, learners should be encouraged to develop the following study habits: 1) studying at definite time and place; 2) arranging physical environment favorable for study; 3) keeping study materials in order; 4) studying assignment sooner after it is made; 5) looking up familiar words; 6) reviewing lessons before taking examinations; and 7) staying at learning task until it is completed. He said further that teachers of all academic subjects should provide training for developing the learners' study habits and skills.

Moorie (2023) said that good study habits should be started at the right foot. Ten (10) tips which are keys to learning are suggested to have effective study: 1) don't overload; 2) get involved; 3) set goals; 4) use a planner; 5) learn to prioritize; 6) don't procrastinate; 7) don't fly solo; 8) have a break; 9) don't get too comfortable; and 10) stay calm.

On Parents' Assistance

The parents/family is another factor which can possibly influence children. Dalope (2024) pointed out that aside from the school, the home is the greatest single factor in character

formation. It is the first environment in which the child's character is shaped. The home is the place where the children learns his first lessons, meet his first problems and has the first contact with life.

The parents or the family is a typical primary group that touches and molds the individual first and it is the vehicle of the deepest lifelong emotions. The family serves as an avenue as it stands at the center of one's social life for it links the individual to school, society and the world.

According to Cohen (2024) father's/mother's abandonment, relative absence, or infrequent presence can cause disappointment in a child repeatedly, which usually add to the child's feeling of rejection and cause lower self-esteem. When the parents cut their link off the child, piece of the child's experience is missing. Children who live with parents to guide and assist them have more significant advantage over those children who live without parents. Intact families have more positive effects on children.

Summary of the Reviewed Literature and Studies to the Present Study

Ramon (2024) in his study which sought to determine the relationship between Filipino 7 performance and teacher-related factors among Grade 7 learners in the District of San Juan. He revealed the following:

1. The Grade 7 learners had a high level of performance in the basic Filipino 7 process skills.
2. The elementary schools of San Juan have equipment and facilities and class size described "moderately" adequate.
3. Majority of the learners' mothers are high school graduates while their fathers are college graduates.
4. The respondents' parents are engaged in nonprofessional jobs while most of the learners belong to the lowest bracket income does not affect significantly the learners' performance in Filipino 7.

Ramon's study and the present study are similar because both used the descriptive method of research but the two studies are different in the sense that the former made use of Grade 7 learners as respondents while the latter involved the Grade 7I learners as respondents.

Montecalvo (2024) made an analysis on the learning skills and attitude of Grade 7I learners in Linamon, Division of Lanao del Norte. He found out that the respondents have average level of skills, likewise, they have fair level of attitude towards Filipino 7. There is a significant relationship between the learners' level of skills and attitude towards Filipino 7.

Montecalvo's study and the present study have some similarities in some variables like sex, attitude towards Filipino 7 and both studies used the descriptive method of research and grade six learners as respondents.

Burquillos (2023) made a study on the performance in Filipino 7 of 236 Grade 7 learners as affected by economic level of the family such as occupation, income, family size and educational materials found at home and parents' assistance. The researcher made use of descriptive method of research and came up with the following results:

1. Learners with available educational materials at home performed better than those without educational materials.
2. Learners who came from bigger family size and with low income have lower performance compared with learners who belong to small family.
3. Learners who received more assistance from their parents performed very well than those who received less assistance.

The study of Burquillos and the present study are similar in methodology. Both used the descriptive method. The former study made use of the Division Achievement Test and the latter study uses the summative test covering the fourth grading period.

Cariaso (2024) made an investigation which focus on the factor affecting the performance of grade six learners in Filipino 7 such as teacher-related factors and family-related factors, she revealed the following:

1. Majority of the learners have satisfactory performance in Filipino 7 as revealed by the Summative Test results.
2. There is no significant relationship between the learners' level of performance and some related teacher-related factors.
3. There is no significant relationship between the learners' performance and their family-related factors.

Cariaso's study and the present study are similar in the profile variables used. Both used the descriptive method of research and used grade six learners as respondents. The former study included some teacher factors while the latter focuses only on learners' profile variables.

The study of Gerardo (2023) found out that study habits significantly enhances students' attitude towards Filipino 7 and performance level in Filipino 7. Gerardo' study and the present study suggest that learners need to develop good study habits to improve their performance in Filipino 7.

Cavalos (2023) revealed that method of instruction has a significant effect and can contribute to better performance in Filipino 7. The method of instruction is significantly related to the level of learners' performance in Filipino 7. The present study and that of Cavalos are similar in the sense that they both with learners' performance in Filipino 7. The present study, however, does not include method of instruction as variable. It focuses on learners' personal and psychological such as attitude towards Filipino 7 and study habits variables.

Nunez (2023) conducted a study on the performance of learners in Filipino 7. Findings of the study revealed that sex was found out to have a negligible to substantial relations to the difficulties encountered by the respondents in Filipino 7. It was found out that based on the scores of respondents showed that females encountered less difficulties than males.

The present study and that of Nunez dealt with the same variables like sex and performance level. The differences between these studies were the former made use of teachers' variables while the present study use the intellectual and non-intellectual variables of the grade six learners.

The study conducted by Cortez (2023) focused on the difficulties encountered by the learners in Filipino 7 in relation to age, sex, and economic status. She found out that age, sex, and economic status are not predictor variables in providing the degree of difficulties of the respondents in Filipino 7. The study of Cortez and the present study are the same in the sense that both used grade six learners and considered sex as one of the profile variables.

Domingo (2024) revealed that the visual ,logical and spatial oriented teaching of learners in Filipino 7 are significantly correlated with their attitude towards the same subject. Both the former and the present studies are similar in the sense that both used sex, and attitude towards Filipino 7.

Sangco (2023) revealed that grade six learners have positive attitude towards Filipino 7 and have satisfactory performance in Filipino 7. Moreover, the attitude of learners towards Filipino 7 is not influenced by the learners' age and sex. Panda (2022) revealed from her study

on the Filipino 7 achievement of grade six learners that their achievement in Filipino 7 bears significant relationship with the learners' age and gender.

On the evaluation of Martinez, (2023) on the effects of varied teaching approaches and the achievement of the students concluded that using varied teaching approaches is a tool to improve the students' achievement in Filipino 7. .

The present study and the studies of Domingo (2025), Sangco (2022) and Martinez (2023) elicited similarities by way of research variables such as attitude towards Filipino 7 and achievement in Filipino 7. The above-mentioned studies differ from the research method used and the environment where these studies are conducted.

Rojas (2023) conducted a study on the correlates of Mathematics performance among fourth year students in Cagayan. She discovered that the students' learning skills is significantly related with their personal variables such as study habits and parents' assistance.

In a similar study, Ramos (2023) found out that the students' self-concept is also highly related to their learning performance in Physics. It was also noted by Delos Santos (2023) that the students' level of self-concept is significantly related to their performance in NSAT.

Digos (2023) reported the results of her findings that even the gifted children's high performance is significantly related to their self-concept. According to Llamas (1998) self-concept was significantly related with child-rearing practices as well as the academic performance of students in the public high schools.

Soriano (2023) identified in her study that the level of learning skills of students were significantly related with some selected home and personal variables like number of siblings in the family, birth order, parents' occupation, study habits and parents' assistance. She further revealed that the children who received assistance from their parents or siblings obtained higher level of achievement.

Assessment of performance or literacy is one step in exploring the possibilities toward instruction upgrading. It is important to determine the achievement level of the learners in order to find out if they have fully developed or mastered the skills and also to discover the factors or variables that may possibly influence their performance.

The elementary Filipino Revised K to 12 curriculum is developed in terms of meanings and understanding of the different aspects in Filipino 7 that are of interest and are meaningful to the learners. It is designed to develop intelligence with reference to the place of Filipino in everyday life. Although the elementary Filipino 7 curriculum adheres to a desired pattern and sound educational principles in its organization, it is characterized by a great deal of flexibility which means adjustment of the curriculum to the needs and interests of the learners and the utilization of available community resources to the fullest extent (Gregorio, 2024).

Presently, the National Achievement Test results in the country are not improving, as cited by the Secretary of Education (Lapus, 2024). However, the Secretary of Education refers to the data on the NAT results from year 2023 to 2024, which was below 75% proficiency level of Philippines Learning Competence. The percentage scores of Elementary NAT results were 54.50% in 2023; 59.94% in 2024; 64.81 in 2024; 66.33% in 2024 and in 2024 the rate 69.21% on the national level (Benito, 2024). Moreover, these low achievement level of Elementary NAT results can be counted to the percentage scores of Filipino learning area. In the year 2023 the rate was 46.77%, 2024-51.58%, 2024-57.90%, 2024-59.63%. The year 2024, there are 65.03% which made Filipino ranked lowest among the five subjects taken by the learners (NETRC, 2024).

In the 1st District of Basista I Central School, the dismal results of the Division

Achievement Test in Filipino 7 prompted the researcher to conduct this study. Based on the tests results, 78% of the total population of Grade 7 learners in the district obtained scores below the passing percentage which is 75% set by the division office. This prompted the researcher to look into the causes of the low performance of the learners in Filipino.

Based on the above-cited premises, the researcher who is an Filipino teacher herself experiences such dismal performance of her learners in this discipline. Many researches have been conducted as to what really cause this poor performance of the learners using various variables. This research is based on the intellectual and non-intellectual variables of the learners and it is within this parameter that the researcher aimed to determine the level of performance of the learners in Filipino and tried to find out how their intellectual and non-intellectual variables influence or affect their performance.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the theory of Horne 1981 cited by Gregorio et al., (2024) that learning is an experience which occurs inside the learner and is activated by the learner. It is necessary that the learners get motivation to learn. Motivation can be provided not only in the school but primarily in the home. Teachers and parents should work hand-in-hand to provide this motivation to improve their performance in Filipino 7.

Filipino instruction had improved by leaps and bounds that Filipino teachers have continued to enrich it in many ways. These attempts have contributed to meet society's tasks and challenges through the learners who are the activating elements so as to acquire realization of self-fulfillment cited by Aquino, et al., (2025).

The teaching of elementary Filipino aims to develop in the child the scientific attitude that could influence his manner of thinking and ways of doing things. He must be actively involved in the process of observation, discussion, reading and experimentation. In other words, the child must be competent and skilled in the different Filipino 7 processes so that he could put into practice the different scientific ideas and principles.

The elementary Filipino curriculum is developed in terms of meanings and understanding which includes the aspects that are of interest and are meaningful to the learners. It is designed to develop intelligence with reference to the place of Filipino 7 in the learners' everyday life. It is characterized by a great deal of flexibility which means adjustment of the curriculum to the needs and interests of the learners and the utilization of available resources in the community to the fullest extent (Gregorio, 2025).

Filipino teachers are then expected to perform their tasks to a high level of efficiency and sincerity in the exercise of their profession. They should develop among learners skills and scientific attitude that will influence their manner of thinking and ways of doing things.

The improvement of Filipino program in the elementary level presents a challenge to instructional leadership. In this milieu of scientific age, advances in Filipino 7 are continually changing the way people live. The world of the child creates him curiosities and interests which demand satisfaction. The teaching of elementary Filipino 7 should therefore offer a broad range of content to satisfy the many interests of the child.

The task of the Filipino 7 teacher is to create situations which will cause learners to constantly raise questions, test the validity of their ideas, until it becomes a habit and to make an intelligent adult, critical and essentially a doer, receptive to new ideas and are well-equipped to apply these ideas in reality.

Researches have likewise pointed out that the system must pay attention on how the current school and curricular structure develop cognitive skills among the Filipino learners. Acuna (2022) stresses in his study that there is a need to address the present problem on why Filipino learners fail to master the different skills/competencies in Filipino. The fact pointed out to the need to upgrade teaching styles of teachers handling the learning area. How children learn Filipino concepts and gain skills on scientific principles depends upon how the teachers develop these concepts in the classroom. Hence, it is said that the teacher plays an important role in the teaching- learning process.

In the attainment of the foresighted vision, it is imperative for the teachers to teach to the point of mastery. It is in this pursuit that the factors attributed to quality learning shall be provided adequately.

The learner gains the necessary skills and masters the different scientific principles depend largely on how the teachers develop these concepts inside the classroom.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Filipino enables learners to think creatively and critically as it involves inquiry and discovery. The learning situations inside the classroom expose the learners to real and interesting experiences in order that his curiosity is stimulated. To enable the learners to be imaginative and inventive, learners are involved in problem-solving situations.

The researcher believed that certain factors may affect/influence the academic performance of Grade 7 learners in Filipino. This study then, is an assessment of the academic performance of the Grade 7 learners in Filipino in correlation to their intellective and non-intellective variables. From the data that will be gathered, these were statistically treated to test the hypotheses, and the findings became the bases for conclusions and the corresponding recommendations.

Figure 1 presents the schematic diagram showing the relation of the dependent and independent variables of the study.

The independent variables are the intellective variables of the Grade 7 learners in terms of GPA in Grade 7 and the first grading rating in Filipino 7 the non-intellective variables in terms of gender, parental assistance, study habits, self-concepts and attitudes towards Filipino subject.

The dependent variables are the performance of the Grade 7 learners, the first grading (first quarter to third quarter). The results will be the formulation of the proposed measures reflected in the third box to improve the performance of the Grade 7 learners in Filipino.

Figure 1
Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study determined the correlates of the non-intellective and intellective profile variables to the level of performance of the learners in Filipino 7 in Basista, division of Pangasinan I during the school year 2025-2026.

Specifically, it will seek to answers to the following questions:

1. What are the attributes of the Grade 7 learners of the public secondary schools in Basista Division of Pangasinan I during the school year 2025-2026 along:
 - A. Intellective Variables
 - a. GPA in Grade 7, and
 - b. First to Third Grading Rating in Filipino 7 Learners?
 - B. Intellective and Non-Intellective Variables of Filipino 7 Teachers along:

- a. leadership skill;
 - b. distinctive skill;
 - c. critical thinking;
 - d. change skill;
 - e. research skill;
 - f. computer skill (non-intellective); and
 - g. e-learning skill (non-intellective)?
2. What is the performance level of the learners as reveal the first grading to third grading period in Filipino?
 3. Is there a significant relationship between the intellective and non-intellective profile variables of the Grade 7 learners and their academic performance in Filipino?
 4. What factors contributed most to the academic performance of the Grade 7 learners Filipino?
 5. Is there a significant difference between the Grade 7 learners' academic performance across their non-intellective variables in Filipino?
 6. What measures can be proposed to improve the performance of the Grade 7 learners?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses will be tested at .05 level of significance in their null form:

1. There is no significant relationship between the intellective and non-intellective profile variables of the Grade 7 learners.
2. There is no significant difference between the learners' level of performance in Filipino across their non-intellective profile variables.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study will be focused on the Grade 7 learners' level of performance in Filipino in Basista District I Division I of Pangasinan which will be determined through covering the first grading period. It also dealt with the intellective and non-intellective variables and the identification of the factors that significantly explained the relationship in their level of performance in Filipino.

In this study, learners' intellective variables are their GPA in Grade 7 and their first grading rating in Filipino 7 and the non-intellective variables of the learners are gender, parents' assistance, self-concept, study habits and attitude towards Filipino 7.

Significance of the Study

Filipino Knowledge in Filipino language is the key that opens the avenue for great many occupations, careers and professions. The influence of Filipino education to man has made imperative to see to it that learners get the best possible communicative background.

Public Secondary Schools. Competency in Filipino is important to every learner in solving problems of everyday life. The findings of this study will help public elementary school administrators and curriculum planners to work hard towards producing individuals with better developed knowledge, values and skills thereby offering adequate, meaningful and relevant education.

Public School Administrators. The school administrators could also gain insights on the instructional competencies of Filipino teachers and be guided on their supervisory activities so that they can assist these teachers enhance Filipino instruction and therefore produce learners

who are communicatively competent.

Filipino Teachers. This study also enables Filipino teachers to gain information on the achievement of the learners and with these results, they can improve their competencies teaching the subject area. It is also directed to Filipino teachers for having the greatest influence over the learning performance of their learners. This provides the springboard for teachers to reflect on their classroom practices thereby enriching themselves with workable and appropriate instructional approaches since the success and failure of the teaching learning process depends mostly on them being the key implementers of Revised K-12 Curriculum (2024).

Learners. This study is anchored on the ultimate users of knowledge and information shared by the teachers are expected to benefit from this study, to the extent that if this information sharing and knowledge exchange is completely conducted, being the center of the educative process. This could provide insights on how to better improve their achievement in Filipino 7 and how to develop their appreciation for the subject.

Overall, the results of this study would reflect a clear picture on the real status of Filipino 7 instruction. Moreover, it will also provide a holistic and objective plan for improving the achievement of the Grade 7 learners in Filipino.

Results of this study could provide other researchers benchmark data which could be valuable to their studies.

Definition of Terms

In order to facilitate better understanding of the different terms that were used in this study, operational definitions of the terms are given

Academic Performance. This refers to how learners/students deal with their studies and how they cope with or accomplish different tasks given to them by their teachers.

Achievement in Filipino 7. This refers to the degree of mastery skills, fundamental concepts, processes and general knowledge in Filipino. In this study, it refers to the learners' scores in the Achievement Test.

Achievement Test. This refers to a 40-item teacher made test covering the competencies for the first to fourth grading period based on the BEC Learning Competencies.

Attitude Towards Filipino Subject. This refers to the sum total of an individual's feelings, inclinations and preconceived notions which tend to create a disposition or readiness to act on a particular situation (Sally, 2023). In this study it refers to learners' liking of Filipino as a learning area, their perceptions on their competence and their beliefs regarding the process of learning Filipino.

Grade 7 Learners. In this study, they are the sixth school year after kindergarten. Learners are usually 11-12 years of age.

Intellective Variables. In this study, these refer to the pupil' GPA in Grade 7 and their final rating in Filipino subject.

Non-Intellective Variables. As used in this study, these variables include the gender of the learners, their parents' assistance at home with regards to their homework, projects and other activities in Filipino 7, self-concept, study habits and attitude towards Filipino 7.

Parents' Assistance. In this study, it refers to the parents' involvement in the pupil's Filipino 7-related activities like homework, projects, test and quizzes.

Filipino 7 Learning Area in this study refers to learning area where systematic enterprise builds and organizes knowledge in the form of testable explanations and predictions

about the universe. In an older and closely related meaning, it also refers to a body of knowledge itself, of the type that can be rationally explained and reliably applied. As a medium of communication and a tool subject teaching.

Self-Concept. Macklem (2025) defines self-concept as how children think about themselves which is inherently phenomenological which is the person's own view of himself. In this study, this refers to the learners' feelings about their physical appearance, clothing and good grooming, health and physical soundness, enjoyment and recreation.

Chapter 2 METHODOLOGY

This chapter of the study includes the research design, sources of data, instrumentation and data collection, and tools for data analysis.

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational method was used in this study. According to Sevilla, et.al (2025), the descriptive method is designed for the researcher to gather information about existing conditions. Basically, descriptive research answers the question "what is?" In the formulation of a course of action, several sorts of information needed. These data could be gathered through the process of descriptive method of research. The principal aim of employing this method is to describe the nature of a situation as it exists at the time of the study and to explore the causes of the phenomenon.

The descriptive method of research was employed to describe the profile of the Grade 7 learners in terms of their intellectual and non-intellectual variables in Basista Division of Pangasinan I. Likewise, the same descriptive method will be used to describe the Grade 7 learners' academic performance in Filipino 7 based on the Achievement Test that was administered by the researcher covering the 1st to 3rd grading period.

The correlational method is concerned with determining the extent of relationship existing between the variables. It enables one to ascertain the extent to which the variations in one variable are associated with the variable in another. The degree of associations or relationships is determined through the computation of the coefficient of correlation. The correlational procedure enabled the researcher to determine the relationships between the learners' academic performance in Filipino 7 and their intellectual and non-intellectual profile variables.

Sources of the Data

The population that was considered in this study are the Grade 7 learners in the secondary schools of Basista Pangasinan. There are 650 Grade 7 learners. The sample size will be determined using the Slovin's formula as shown below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

where:

n = sample size

N = total population

e = margin of error pegged at .05

After having determined the sample size using the said formula, a total of 82 Grade 7 learners will be used as respondents in this study. Table 1 below shows the frequency distribution of respondents.

Table I
Frequency Distribution of Grade 7 Teachers in Filipino by School

School	Teachers	Grade 7 Learners
1. Basista National School	12	35
2. Bayoyong National School	8	25
3. Dumpay National School	10	22
Total	30	82

Data Gathering Instrument

This study made use of two sets of instruments, namely: Questionnaire and the Achievement Test in Filipino 7. The Questionnaire consists of two parts. Part I gives the background information of the respondents. Part II of the questionnaire calls for the learners' intellectual and non-intellectual variables. It is adopted from the study of Vergara in Master of Arts in Educational Management at Luna Colleges, Tayug, Pangasinan.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the conduct of this study, permission will be sought from the Office of the Schools Division I Superintendent of Pangasinan. The same will be done from the office of the teacher and to the different public elementary school administrators in District I. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire and the Achievement Test to the identified respondents to ensure one hundred (100) percent retrieval and to obtain the needed in this study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To obtain valid and reliable results from the data gathered, appropriate statistical tools were employed by the researcher.

For sub-problem 1.A

For the learners' intellectual variables such as GPA in Grade 7 learners and first grading rating in Filipino 7, the average will be used to interpret the data using an average scale set prior to the study as shown below:

Average Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
95 and above	Very High (VH)
90 - 94	High (H)
85 -89	Moderately High (MH)
80 - 84	Low (L)
75 - 79	Very Low (VL)

For sub-problem 1.B

1. On Learners' non-intellective variables
 - a) Gender will be determined using frequency counts and percentages.
 - b) For parents' assistance, the average weighted mean will be used and a 5-point Likert scale will be used and be interpreted using the following scale values:

Scale Value	Descriptive Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Very Often (VO)
3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)
2.61 – 3.40	Seldom (Se)
1.81 – 2.60	Sometimes (So)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)

- c) For the learners' study habits, a 5-point Likert scale will be used and will be interpreted using the following scale values:

Scale Value	Descriptive Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Very Desirable (VD)
3.41 – 4.20	Desirable (D)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Desirable (MD)
1.81 – 2.60	Fairly Desirable (FD)
1.00 – 1.80	Not Desirable (ND)

- d) For the learners' level of self-concept, the average weighted mean will be used and the results will be interpreted using a 3-point scale shown scale shown below:

Scale Value	Descriptive Equivalent
2.34 - 3.00	High (H)
1.67 – 2.33	Moderately High (MH)
1.00 - 1.66	Low (L)

- e) For the learners' attitude towards Filipino 7, a five-point scale will be used to interpret the attitude of the learners. These are:

- 5 - Strongly Agree (SA)
- 4 - Agree (A)
- 3 - Uncertain (U)
- 2 - Disagree (D)
- 1 - Strongly Disagree (SD)

Learners' general attitude towards Filipino will be categorized as positive, uncertain and negative. Responses that fall under disagree and strongly disagree were classified as negative attitude. And responses that fall under strongly agree and agree were classified as positive attitude. This scheme is shown below:

Scale Value	Descriptive Equivalent	Category
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Highly Positive
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	Positive
2.61 – 3.40	Uncertain (U)	Fair
1.81 - 2.60	Disagree (DA)	Negative
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SA)	Highly Negative

For sub-problem 2

For the performance level of the learners based on the first grading ratings in Filipino 7, the following score range will be used to interpret the results:

Test Score Range	Descriptive Equivalent
95 and above	Very High (VH)
90 – 94	High (H)
85 – 89	Moderately High (MH)
80 – 84	Low (L)
75 – 79	Very Low (VL)

For sub-problem 3

The relationship between the non-intellective and intellective profile variables of the Grade 7 learners and their academic performance in Filipino 7 was determined using the Pearson (r) Product Moment of Correlation formula. In the interpretation of the coefficient of correlation, the following guide evolved by Garret (1964) cited by Gregorio (2024) will be used:

Coefficient of Correlation	Interpretation
0.00	no correlation
.01 - + .20	negligible relationship
-.21 to -+ .40	low/slight correlation
-.41 to -+ .70	moderate correlation
-.71 to -+ .90	high correlation
-.91 to -+ .99	very high correlation
-+ 1.00	perfect correlation

For sub-problem 5

The significant difference between the Grade 7 learners' academic performance across their non-intellective variables in Filipino will be determined using the t-test.

Chapter 3
RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter dealt on the presentation analysis and interpretation of data gathered with the utilization of the validated questionnaire. The data were analyzed using some statistical tools and descriptive method to come up with some findings, conclusions and recommendations of this study.

The data presented in this chapter dealt on the academic performance of learners in Filipino 7 and non-intellect skills of the public-school teachers in the three public secondary schools in Basista, Pangasinan during the school year 2025-2026 with the following sub-problems: leadership skill, distinctive skill, critical thinking, change skill, research skill, computer skill, and e-learning skill.

Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-School Teachers along Leadership Skills

Table 2 dealt on the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the along leadership skills as perceived by the public-school teachers themselves.

It is noticeable that sub-indicators on leadership skills on moral qualities such as respect, appreciation, reliability time respect as moderate in the two group of respondents proven by 3.39 (ME) and 3.71 (ME) respectively. This implied that the moderate appraisal of respondents on moral qualities manifested mainly on the core values of the school proven by the total average weighted mean of 3.55 (ME).

It could also be noticed that on diversities in using movements, gestures, raising and lowering of sounds in teaching situations as moderate proven by the response of the school head 2.59 (ME) and their chiefs at 3.11 (ME). This only implied that diversities in leadership skills of the public teachers are ready to face challenges and changes in the implementation of programs in the division level.

Table 2
Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers along Leadership Skills

A. Leadership Skills					Overall	AWR
	WM	DE	WM	DE		
1. Has moral qualities such as respect, appreciation, reliability time respect.	3.39	ME	3.71	ME	3.55	ME
2. Acts properly in educational situations inside and outside classroom / school.	3.15	ME	3.07	ME	3.11	ME
3. Diversifies in using movements, gestures, raising and lowering of sounds in teaching situations.	2.59	ME	3.11	ME	2.85	ME
4. Cares for external look's / outlook to attract attention of students	3.15	ME	3.23	ME	3.19	ME
5. Has self-control and make suitable decision during teaching.	2.78	ME	3.44	ME	3.11	ME
6. Has charisma of positive leadership that reflects long experience in teaching.	2.81	ME	3.25	ME	3.03	ME

7. Practices modern leadership roles in teaching e.g. control, guidance, coordination.	2.93	ME	3.21	ME	3.07	ME
8. Has intellectual fluency to manage time reflected in prudence and linguistic intelligence.	3.12	ME	3.36	ME	3.24	ME
Overall Average Weighted Mean	2.99	ME	3.30	ME	3.14	ME

Overall, the eight indicators under the leadership skills was moderate proven by the response of the school head 2.99 (ME) and their chief in CID 3.30 (ME) respectively. Further, the overall weighted mean was moderate proven by 3.14 (ME), this implied that positive leadership, charisma, intellectual fluency and care rendered by the school head in their respective schools did not achieved higher ratings.

This only implies that the enhancement of intellect and non-intellect skills of the particularly the fourteen (14) Division Offices in Region I was existing but not consistent, under construed and lacks strong remarks as perceived by the two group of respondents.

Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers along Distinctive Skills

Table 3 dealt on the level of intellect and non-intellect skills along distinctive skills as perceived by the public-school teachers themselves.

Table 3

Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers along Distinctive Skills

B. Distinctive Skills					Overall	AWR
	WM	DE	WM	DE		
1. Arranges priorities to accomplish the required tasks relevant to language without direct supervision.	3.33	ME	3.43	ME	3.38	ME
2. Has the ability to be self-autonomous in obtaining knowledge	3.13	ME	3.55	ME	3.34	ME
3. Prepares pioneering education environment for linguistic creativity.	2.64	ME	3.16	ME	2.90	ME
4. Shows willingness for excellence in teaching.	3.03	ME	3.30	ME	3.16	ME
5. Take initiative to accomplish language duties before due time.	3.10	ME	3.16	ME	3.13	ME
6. Adopts modern methods and techniques in dealing with students with special needs.	3.01	ME	3.43	ME	3.22	ME
7. Heads for international events that discuss various language issues.	2.98	ME	3.23	ME	3.10	ME
8. Raises analytical, contemplative and	3.08	ME	3.45	ME	3.27	ME

critical vision of learners.						
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.04	ME	3.34	ME	3.19	ME

It could be observed that on the distinctive skills arranges priorities to accomplish the required tasks relevant to language without direct supervision was moderate extent proven by the average weighted mean as perceived by both respondents 3.33 (ME), has the ability to be self-autonomous in obtaining knowledge 3.13 (ME), and raises analytical, contemplative and critical vision of learners 3.08 (ME). The findings implied that the school head failed to ensure strong sense of pioneer techniques in linguistic creativity, take initiative to adopt innovative methodology for school and efficiently carry-out their school activities as necessary and not as voluntarily and heartily accomplish. It meant that some of the school head did not fully realize the value of distinctive skills in supervision proven by 3.19 (ME).

It could be noted that indicator promote initiatives to uplift the learning outcomes of the learners and increased utilization of modern methods and techniques in dealing with the students with special needs viewed by the school head as least extent proven by the weighted means of 2.64 (ME) and 3.16 (ME) respectively. This only implied that the learners lacking pioneering education environment for linguistic creativity, hence promoting the same will develop self-value and care for their well-being of the learners.

As a whole, both respondents perceived all the indicators under the distinctive skills as moderate in extent proven by the overall combined weighted mean of 3.19 (ME). This only implied that some of the school head failed to accomplish their roles as supervisors and implementers of educational support system in their schools.

Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers along Critical Skills

Table 4 dealt on the level of intellect and non-intellect skills vis-a-vis along critical skills as perceived by the public-school teachers themselves.

Table 4

Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers along Critical Skills

C. Critical Skills					Overall	AWR
	WM	DE	WM	DE		
1. Uses decision making techniques that develop short and long -term plan for the school.	3.30	ME	3.30	ME	3.30	ME
2. Has the ability to create options and techniques on how to win the minds of stakeholders.	3.13	ME	3.55	ME	3.34	ME
3. Employs education situations that requires analysis, structuring, providing alternatives in supervision.	2.64	ME	2.65	ME	2.64	ME
4. Urges school heads to critically and innovatively manage their schools.	3.15	ME	3.15	ME	3.15	ME
5. Benchmark best practices in school governance council of other school.	3.10	ME	3.16	ME	3.13	ME

6. Adopts modern techniques and methodology in leading the school through appropriate school-based management assessment.	3.01	ME	3.43	ME	3.22	ME
7. Involve the stakeholders in decision making process and crafting relevant ideas to effectively manage the skills of the teachers.	3.10	ME	3.20	ME	3.15	ME
8. Have an updated profiling of teachers to enhanced their capability and effectiveness in delivering quality instructions.	3.08	ME	3.44	ME	3.26	ME
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.06	ME	3.24	ME	3.15	ME

It could be observed that on Uses decision making techniques that develop short and long-term plan for the school was moderate extent proven by the average weighted mean as perceived by both respondents 3.30 (ME), has the ability to create options and techniques on how to win the minds of stakeholders. 3.34 (ME), and Employs education situations that requires analysis, structuring, providing alternatives in supervision 2.64 (ME). The findings implied that the school head did not excel in critical thinking process, failed on some aspects in creating intelligently crafted ideas to enhance the delivery of instructions. It meant that some of the school head failed to monitor the schools to improve their decision making with maximized collaboration of their stakeholders.

It could be noted that indicator urges school heads to critically and innovatively manage their schools. and benchmark best practices in school governance council of other school viewed by the school head as moderate extent proven by the weighted means of 3.15 (ME) and 3.13 (ME) respectively. This only implied that the school head did not accurately pointed out the prevailing problems in their respective districts.

In a nutshell, both respondents perceived all the indicators along critical thinking skills as moderate in extent proven by the overall combined weighted mean of 3.15 (ME). This only implied that some of the school head failed to strengthen their school heads to decide wisely and to come up with a target to be accomplish realistically and systematically within the school year.

Level of Intellect and non-intellect Skills of the Public-school Teachers along Change Skills

Table 5 dealt on the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the along change skills as perceived by the public-school teachers themselves.

It could be observed that on organizes curriculum evaluation was moderate proven by the combined average weighted mean of 3.39 (ME). This only implied that both respondents could not agree less that there is a need to enhance the medium and long-term plan in the implementation of programs, projects and activities of schools. This also implied that the annual improvement plan and enhance school improvement plan must include targets on support program for learners.

Table 5
Level of Intellect and Non-intellect Skills of the Public-school Teachers along Change Skills

D. Change Skills					Overall	AWR
	WM	DE	WM	DE		
1. Organizes curriculum evaluation	3.38	ME	3.40	ME	3.39	ME
2. Applies new ideas to change stereotype image in supervision skills.	3.27	ME	3.09	ME	3.18	ME
3. Verifies reliability and accuracy of ideas presented for monitoring schools.	3.01	ME	3.13	ME	3.07	ME
4. Encourage research, development and experimentation in supervision process.	3.15	ME	3.25	ME	3.20	ME
5. Organizes experience in data collection for division monitoring evaluation and adjustments.	3.04	ME	3.40	ME	3.22	ME
6. Develop Curriculum Content using interactive method to enhanced learning outcomes.	3.09	ME	3.29	ME	3.19	ME
7. Keeps paces with development and change through new construction to the supervision techniques.	3.01	ME	3.21	ME	3.16	ME
8. Develop skills of achieving self-phasing in creating schedule for supervision.	3.13	ME	3.36	ME	3.24	ME
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.14	ME	3.27	ME	3.21	ME

It could be observed that on organizes curriculum evaluation was moderate proven by the combined average weighted mean of 3.39 (ME). This only implied that both respondents could not agree less that there is a need to enhance the medium and long-term plan in the implementation of programs, projects and activities of schools. This also implied that the annual improvement plan and enhance school improvement plan must include targets on support program for learners.

It could further be deduced that on keeps paces with development and change through new construction to the linguistic field was perceived by the two groups of respondents as moderate in extent proven by the combined average weighted mean of 3.16 (ME). Likewise, it implied that learners must not be seeing change skills as equally important with other hard skills being portray by the public teachers in their respective division offices.

It could be noticed that on develop skills of achieving self-developing in students such as decision making, criticism, dialogue etc. it was perceived to be moderate in extent proven by the combined average weighted mean of 3.24 (ME). This implied that the support system must involve parents to promote communication and strong bond and cooperation should be monitored by the supervisors in the field to address the gaps.

It could equally be observed that both respondents perceived that encourage research, development and experimentation in teaching was moderate in extent proven by the total average

weighted mean of 3.20 (ME). This suggested that there are some concerns that needs to be filled by the school and the learners at home were family thrive, the learning to be able to happen effectively must observed the vision and mission of the DepEd not only the teaching and administration but also in strong cooperation of its stakeholders.

Level of Intellect and non-intellect Skills of the Public-school Teachers along Research Skills

Table 6 dealt on the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the along research skills as perceived by the public-school teachers themselves.

Table 6
Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers along Research Skills

E. Research Skills					Overall	AWR
	WM	DE	WM	DE		
1. Encourages students to use modern technology in teaching process e.g. electronic dictionary, books, and audio visual aids.	3.09	ME	3.33	ME	3.21	ME
2. Guides to information resources and language cognition via content	3.15	ME	3.07	ME	3.11	ME
3. Is able to discover texts copied from the internet by students	3.02	ME	3.11	ME	3.07	ME
4. Is aware of copyrights issues and the legal use of the Internet	3.15	ME	3.23	ME	3.19	ME
5. Has self-learning skills using digital library to search for language related topics.	3.09	ME	3.44	HE	3.26	ME
6. Is able to conduct an electronic research.	3.13	ME	3.25	ME	3.19	ME
7. Use blogs and Wikipedia to design electronic platforms for learners	3.11	ME	3.21	ME	3.16	ME
8. Follows up updates through digital and paper search academically	3.19	ME	3.36	ME	3.28	ME
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.12	ME	3.25	ME	3.18	ME

It could be observed that on encourages students to use modern technology in teaching process e.g. electronic dictionary, books, and audio-visual aids were moderate proven by the combined average weighted mean of 3.21 (ME). This only implied that both respondents could not agree less that there is a need to enhance the strong cooperation between the learners and the school community in implementing programs of the schools. This also implied that the research is everyone’s task and have a role to play in order to promote the effective conduct of the program.

It could further be deduced that on aware of copyrights issues and the legal use of the Internet was perceived by the two groups of respondents as moderate in extent proven by the combined average weighted mean of 3.19 (ME). On the indicator has self-learning skills using digital library to search for language related topics it was noted as moderate proven by the weighted average mean of 3.26 (ME). This implied that supervision of programs must be revisited to monitor the effectiveness.

In a nutshell, both respondents perceived that effects of research skills were moderate in extent proven by the total average weighted mean of 3.18 (ME). This only implied that the problems in the schools are not be process through research, investigation or focus group study accordingly in order to have appropriate actions to be taken for the well-being and welfare of the learners and effective delivery of instructions through quality interventions by the teachers.

Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers along Computer Skills

Table 7 dealt on the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the along computer skills as perceived by the public-school teachers themselves.

It could be noticed that on knows how to deal with computer programs like word, power point and excel was perceived by the two groups of respondents as moderate in extent proven by the combined average weighted mean of 3.08 (ME). On the indicator can use screen casting tools to create and exchange lesson with others it was noted as moderate proven by the weighted average mean of 3.30 (ME). This implied that supervision of programs must be revisited to monitor the effectiveness in terms of utilization of computer skills.

Table 7
Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers along Computer Skills

F. Computer Skills					Overall	AWR
	WM	DE	WM	DE		
1. Has computer skills and knows how to correctly deal with it.	3.22	ME	3.31	ME	3.26	ME
2. Knows how to deal with computer programs like word, power point and excel	3.10	ME	3.07	ME	3.08	ME
3. Can design and produce computer education program.	3.06	ME	3.11	ME	3.08	ME
4. Can create a e-portfolio related to Philippine aspect	3.03	ME	3.13	ME	3.08	ME
5. Can use screen casting tools to create and exchange lesson with others.	3.33	ME	3.27	ME	3.30	ME
6. Can record and create lessons on computer monitor in sound and image	3.14	ME	3.25	ME	3.20	ME
7. Can create favorite web pages and quote	3.08	ME	3.22	ME	3.15	ME

text to share with students on the net.						
8. Uses drawing tools, post remarks to attract interesting language ideas.	3.19	ME	3.16	ME	3.18	ME
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.14	ME	3.19	ME	3.17	ME

In a nutshell, both respondents perceived that effects of computer skills were moderate in extent proven by the total average weighted mean of 3.17 (ME). This only implied that supervisors did not maximized their skills in utilization of computer to enhanced their reports and innovations in the field.

Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers along E-Learning Skills

Table 8 dealt on the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the along e-learning skills as perceived by the public-school teachers themselves.

Table 8
Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers along E-Learning Skills

G. E-Learning Skills					Overall	AWR
	WM	DE	WM	DE		
1. Merges information technology and communication skills into teaching.	3.20	ME	3.21	ME	3.20	ME
2. Utilizes e-offers and interactive education program with skills in teaching.	3.20	ME	3.09	ME	3.15	ME
3. Uses YouTube in class for purposes related to language.	3.19	ME	3.13	ME	3.16	ME
4. Uses a voting tool to create questionnaire at suitable time.	3.15	ME	3.22	ME	3.18	ME
5. Utilizes computer games for education purposes.	3.21	ME	3.31	ME	3.26	ME
6. Uses digital evaluation tools to create e-test.	3.12	ME	3.15	ME	3.14	ME
7. Employs digital images in class while teaching language content.	3.17	ME	3.20	ME	3.18	ME
8. Participates in producing electronic teaching programs that consolidates self-teaching in all core subjects.	3.12	ME	3.31	ME	3.22	ME
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.17	ME	3.20	ME	3.18	ME

It could be observed that on Participates in producing electronic teaching programs that consolidates self-teaching in all core subjects it was perceived to be moderate in extent proven

by the combined average weighted mean of 3.22 (ME). This implied that supervisors must consolidate reports to inform the top management on the issues, gaps and concerns.

It could be deduced based on the results that both respondents perceived that under electronic learning skills was moderate in extent proven by the total average weighted mean of 3.18 (ME). This suggested that there are some concerns that needs to be proactive in using electronic-learning skills at home, office and in the field.

Summary of the Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers in Filipino 7 along the Seven (7) Sub-Indicators

The table 9 presents the summary on the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the along the seven (7) dimensional skills as perceived by the public-school teachers themselves.

Table 9
Summary of the Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers Along the Seven (7) Sub-Indicators

Summary of the Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers Along the Seven (7) Sub-Indicators					Overall	
	AWM	DE	AWM	DE	AWM	DE
A. Leadership Skills	2.99	ME	3.30	ME	3.14	ME
B. Distinctive Skills	3.04	ME	3.34	ME	3.19	ME
C. Critical Thinking Skills	3.06	ME	3.24	ME	3.15	ME
D. Change Skills	3.14	ME	3.27	ME	3.21	ME
E. Research Skills	3.12	ME	3.25	ME	3.18	ME
F. Computer Skills	3.14	ME	3.19	ME	3.17	ME
G. E-Learning Skills	3.17	ME	3.20	ME	3.18	ME
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.10	ME	3.27	ME	3.18	ME

The summary revealed that on the seven dimensions of the level of hard skills and soft skills of the public-school teachers was moderate in extent proven by the computed overall weighted average mean of 3.18 (ME). This implied that all indicators are similar in extent as perceived by both school head and their chiefs in their functional division.

Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Public-school Teachers and their Principals on the Level of Intellect and Non-intellect skills along the Seven (7) Sub-Indicators

Table 10 dealt on the differences in the perceptions of the Filipino 7 teacher along the seven (7) dimensions of intellect and non-intellect for the school year 2025-2026.

Table 10

Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Public-school Teachers and their Principals on the Level of Intellect and Non-intellect skills along the Seven (7) Sub-Indicators

Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Public-school Teachers on the Level of Intellect and non-intellect skills of the Public-school Teachers along the Seven (7) Sub-Indicators				
	AWM	DE	AWM	DE
A. Leadership Skills	2.99	ME	3.30	ME
B. Distinctive Skills	3.04	ME	3.34	ME
C. Critical Thinking Skills	3.06	ME	3.24	ME
D. Change Skills	3.14	ME	3.27	ME
E. Research Skills	3.12	ME	3.25	ME
F. Computer Skills	3.14	ME	3.19	ME
G. E-Learning Skills	3.17	ME	3.20	ME
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.10	ME	3.27	ME

Computed t-value: 0.00388 @ df 6
 Alpha: @ .05 level of significance
 Critical Value: 1.9432 tabulated @ degrees of freedom of (n-1)
 Decision: Accept the null hypothesis
 Interpretation: No significant difference

The data revealed the difference between the perception of the public-school teachers and their principals along the seven dimensions, the computed t-value (computed in 1 tail distribution and paired variance) and the critical t-value are 0.0388 and 1.9432 respectively. It showed that the computed value is lesser than the critical t-value therefore the null hypothesis is therefore accepted. Hence, there was no significant difference between the perceptions of the two (2) groups of respondents at the .05 level of significance and degrees of freedom (df₆).

This basically implied that the perceptions of the two groups of respondents do not vary from each other proven by the statistical computation and validation in the statistical references.

Relationship Between the Perceptions of the Public-school Teachers and their Principals Seven (7) Dimensional Skills of Supervisor

The Pearson Product Moment of Coefficient of Correlation was used in determining the relationship between the response in the seven (7) dimensions under intellect and non-intellect skills of the results could be gleaned in Table 11 below.

Table 11 presented the relationship between the perceptions of the themselves and their Curriculum and Instruction Division Chiefs in their level of intellect and non-intellect skills.

The result showed that there was no significant relationship in terms of leadership skills as revealed in the r-value of .020 and a significant of .775 which is negligible correlation. This meant that even though the respondents were younger or older when it comes to their leadership, it is non-negotiable to note.

Likewise, there was no significant relationship occurred between the distinctive skills and the response of the teachers. This is proven by r-value of .045 and .562 significant difference thus it had negligible correlation.

Moreover, there was negligible correlation existed between the critical thinking skills, proven by r-value of .148 and a significance of .479, thus it means that even though the respondents were pressured through the bulk of reports and deadline of submission of reports, they still manage to compensate and deliver necessary tasks on time.

Table 11
Relationship between the Perceptions of the Filipino 7 Teachers Themselves and their Principals in their Level of Intellect and Non-intellect Skills

Intellect and non-intellect skills of the	Intellect and non-intellect skills		Description
	R – value	Significance	
A. Leadership Skills	.020	.775	Low
B. Distinctive Skills	.045	.562	Low
C. Critical Thinking Skills	.148	.479	Moderate
D. Change Skills	.185	.054	Low
E. Research Skills	.148	.016	Moderate
F. Computer Skills	.055	.054	Moderate
G. E-Learning Skills	.035	.479	Low
r-value	.020		Not significant

Significant at .05 Alpha

Result: No significant relationship

On the other hand, there was low correlation existed on research skills noted by r-value of .148 and a significance of .016. It meant that there was a slight effect of the number of implemented action researches produced by the district although approved and funded.

Likewise, there was low correlation existed on computer skills proven by r-value of .055 and a significance of .054. It meant that respondents needed to embrace the fast changes in the utilization of computer devices.

Lastly, on the computer skills there was no correlation, proven by the r-value of .020 (NS) and a significance of .054 (ME). It meant that the even though the respondents attended much or less seminars and trainings it had no effect on the problems encountered by them on the utilization of computer skills in supervision process. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Proposed Intervention Program to Enhance the Level of Intellect and Non-intellect Skills of the Filipino 7 Teachers along the Seven (7) Sub-Indicators

The proposed intervention program is a comprehensive one for the enhancement of the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the public-school teachers along the seven sub-indicators, strategies based from the analysis of the data on the said variables of the study, firstly the soft skills: leadership skills, distinctive skills, critical thinking skills, change skills, and research skills and secondly, the hard skills: computer skills and electronic learning skills in the municipality of Basista, Pangasinan. the action plan is in the form of table consisted of the following parts.

1. Areas of Concern
2. Objectives
3. Strategies / Activities
4. Time Frame
5. People Involved
6. Success Indicator

General Objective:

The level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the public-school teachers in the fourteen offices in Region I during the school year 2025-2026 is essential to determine in order to assess their leadership skill, distinctive skill, critical thinking, change skill, research skill, computer skill, and e-learning skill. Views of the public teachers and their chief education supervisor in curriculum and instruction division are also important to note in order to closed the gaps and proposed intervention. This plan of action is to enhanced the intellect and non-intellect skills of the public-school teachers in the municipality of Basista, Pangasinan.

Proposed Intervention Program to Enhance the Level of Intellect and Non-intellect Skills of the Filipino 7 Teachers

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Strategies/Activities	Time Frame	People Involved	Success Indicator
A. Intellective (Leadership, Distinctive, Critical Thinking, Change and Research Skills)					
1. Promoting effective supervision through an enhanced intellect and non-intellect skills of the Filipino 7 teachers 2. Purposive and proactive supervision to enhanced environment that encourage positive learning outcome	1. Evaluate schools and identify the needs to promote improvement of the learning outcome through a functional school governance council (SGC). 2. Encourage school heads to craft school improvement plan and annual improvement plan with sustainable targeted goals.	1. Involve techniques in giving home activities by the learners. 2. Capacitate and Orient Filipino 7 teachers by providing trainings and online courses to enhance their skills. 3. Master time management and relay the technique to parents which they will carry-out at home for the follow-up of learning.	As needed and depending on the school calendar and availability of fund	CID and SGOD Chiefs, , EPSs, , School Heads, Teachers, Parents, SEPS Monitoring and Evaluation and the Learners	95% of the teachers shall have actively attend sessions and produce output on intellect and non-intellect skills enhancement . 95% of the teachers attended the course conducted by the expert vis-a-vis intellect and non-intellect skills development and intensification.
1. Provide the learners with flexible system of learning at	1. Encourage the learners to meditate and follow the steps given by the	1. Discuss with the parents and learners about the possible impact of the	As needed and depending on the school	, EPSs, Teacher, School Heads, Parents, SEPS	90% of the teachers shall have identified areas that affect the

<p>home to give them peace of mind.</p> <p>a. Encourage the learners to give feedback of their struggle and learning difficulty to be prompt with action.</p> <p>b. Identificat ion of a variables that affects the well-being of learners at school.</p>	<p>school heads.</p> <p>2. Be informed of all the happenings around the surrounding</p>	<p>home learning and how to cope with it for the learners' welfare and mental stability.</p> <p>2. Manage learners' emotions and anxiety by giving a positive outlook in life while (learner's voice).</p> <p>3. Observe child/childre n for possible intervention and coping mechanism to improve their learning outcomes.</p>	<p>calendar and availabili ty of fund</p>	<p>Monitorin g and Evaluatio n and the Learners and all others concerne d</p>	<p>mental state of the learners by closely working with the division field technical assistance team.</p> <p>98% of the teachers shall have identified the factors that add up to their programs, projects and activities.</p>
<p>1. Strengthen School Governance Council and the School-Based Managemen t System.</p> <p>a. Strengthen teachers on the promotion of the rights</p>	<p>1. Revisit the child protection policy and evaluate its implementati on</p> <p>2. Identify the problems met by the learners at home by updating their</p>	<p>1. Recalibrate the plan based on the need of the schools and propose suitable intervention.</p> <p>2. Plan ahead of time because time is of the essence.</p> <p>3. Meet stakeholders and</p>	<p>As schedule d and as necessary</p>	<p>Teachers Learners Parents School Heads and Curriculu m Planners</p>	<p>90% of the teachers shall have identified means to strengthen the information drive to promote programs, projects and activities in their</p>

<p>and welfare of the learners even the learning modality is distance learning.</p> <p>b. Encourage teachers to consider holistic approach using the best information drive to dissemination.</p>	<p>anecdotal records in the school.</p>	<p>discuss/remind their roles in managing an effective school.</p>			<p>respective districts.</p>
<p>1. Promotion of strong commitment by the internal and external stakeholders.</p> <p>a. Developed a learning plan that targets problematic areas in learning outcome.</p> <p>b. Encourage school heads to consider holistic</p>	<p>1. Prepare a schedule for stakeholders' short debriefing of their roles in support of their curriculum and governance activities.</p> <p>2. Promote simple stakeholders' consultation especially in conducting extra-curricular activities of the teachers and</p>	<p>1. Create systematic program where teachers can open up problems with their parents through a medium and effective interventions.</p> <p>2. Meeting with the top management to air problems gathered within the district for summary report to be</p>	<p>As scheduled and as necessary</p>	<p>Teachers Pupils Parents School Heads and Curriculum Planners</p>	<p>90% of the teachers shall have identified problematic areas that affects the relationships of variables to improve learning outcomes and account the results by making a simply statistics or action research.</p>

<p>view and bridge the gap by engaging stakeholders to strengthen the shared governance approach.</p>	<p>learners in each school.</p>	<p>discussed during the Division Learning Action Cell (LAC sessions).</p>			
<p>B. Non-Intellect (Computer Skills and Electronic-Learning Skills)</p>					
<p>a. Strengthen the utilization of computer assisted programs and application (modernize and e-transaction to track the progress of each supervision and to key-in results for revalidation of programs, projects and activities of the schools).</p>	<p>1. Regularly inform the information and communication technology focal person in each school to maximized their potential in making innovations to increase the level of best practices using the aid of computer applications and programs.</p>	<p>1. Conduct quarterly meeting weekly during the implementation of programs, projects and activities in the school. 2. Gather feedback directly from the school heads whom will be closely monitored by the division personnel under curriculum implementation on division (CID).</p>	<p>Weekly as possible during the SY 2023-2024.</p>	<p>Teachers, Parents, School Heads, and all others concerned</p>	<p>90% of the prevailing problems of the teachers have been recognized addressing the needs to obtain a positive response from the parents, community, LGU and others stakeholders.</p>

Chapter 4

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations made after the analysis of data.

Summary of Findings

This research aimed to assess the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the public-school teachers in three (3) public secondary schools in the municipality of Basista, Pangasinan during the school year 2025-2026 with the following sub-problems: leadership skill, distinctive skill, critical thinking, change skill, research skill, computer skill, and e-learning skill. Secondly, the comparison of the perceptions of the public teachers and their school heads responses. Thirdly, the relationship of the variables along intellect and non-intellect skills of the respondents. Lastly, the plan of action to enhanced the intellect and non-intellect skills of the public-school teachers in the three public secondary schools in Basista, Pangasinan.

Nonetheless, it seeks to answers to the significant sub-questions: what is the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the public-school teachers in the fourteen offices in Region I as perceived by themselves and their school heads along the following dimensions: leadership skill, distinctive skill, critical thinking, change skill, research skill, computer skill, and e-learning skill. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of and their school heads in the level of awareness of intellect and non-intellect skills along the seven (7) dimensions; what is the relationship in the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the along their work output, what measures can be proposed to improve / enhance the intellect and non-intellect skills of , the results of the analysis of the different variables lead the research to propose an action plan to enhance the implementation of the intellect and non-intellect skills of the Filipino 7 teachers in the vis-a-vis academic performance of grade 7 learners in the three (3) public secondary schools in Basista, Pangasinan.

Findings

The contextual analysis of the data resulted to the following salient findings:

1. Under the sub-problems on hard skills of the public-school teachers (school head) along leadership skills was moderate proven by the total overall weighted average mean of 3.14 (ME). Along the distinctive skills of the Filipino 7 teachers, both respondents perceived moderately proven by the overall combined weighted mean of 3.19 (ME). Both respondents perceived along the indicator of critical skills was moderate in extent proven by the overall average weighted average mean of 3.15 (ME). Along change skills, both respondents perceived moderate in extent proven by the total average weighted mean of 3.21 (ME). Both respondents perceived along the research skills was moderate in extent in proven by the overall average weighted average mean of 3.18 (ME).
2. Under the sub-problems on soft skills of the public-school teachers along their computer skills was moderate proven by the average weighted mean of 3.17 (ME) and along e-learning skills was moderate proven by the average weighted mean of 3.18 (ME).
3. There is no significant difference in the perceptions of the public-school teachers and their school heads in the curriculum and instruction division proven by the computed t-value of 0.00388 @ df 6, and tabulated t-value of 1.9432 respectively.
3. There is no significant relationship between the public-school teachers and their intellect and non-intellect skills proven by the computed pearson correlation value of 0.20.
4. An action plan to enhance the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the public-school

teachers was therefore proposed.

Conclusions

The analysis of the findings was yielded the following conclusions.

1. The public-school teachers and their school heads in curriculum and instruction division both agree that on the level of intellect and non-intellect skills along leadership skills, distinctive skills, critical skills, change skills, and research skills, failed to manifest in proven by the results and findings of this study. The intellect skills on computer and e-learning lacks enhancement evident by the results of the findings, this can be associated with the low intake of seminars and trainings for the enhancement of skills of public-school teachers. They were not totally assessed with regard to their intellect and non-intellect skills that are essential in their duties and responsibilities in supervising and monitoring the programs, projects, and activities in their respective schools.
2. The perceptions of the public-school teachers and their school heads did not contradict each other in the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the school head during the full implementation of various programs, projects and activities of the schools.
3. The relationship between the perception of the two group of respondents and their level of intellect and non-intellect skills did not differ much.
4. An action plan primarily to the enhance the level of intellect and non-intellect skills of the Filipino 7 teachers will be proposed.

Recommendations

The following were respectfully recommended by the researcher after analyzing the findings and conclusions.

1. Filipino 7 teachers may pursue to address their issues and concerns, challenges encountered, recommendation of stakeholders for better implementation of various programs, projects and activities through the strengthened manifestation of their intellect and non-intellect skills. should work with their school heads to create an avenue to communicate with parents, Local Government Unit (LGU) and other stakeholders for the information drive and campaign of school-based program. School Governance Council should create a platform to reach those stakeholders and discuss the plan for school year, school calendar of activities and the information-drive campaign.
2. Collaborative sessions and support within the district for the Filipino7 teachers must employ effective intellect and non-intellect skills in dealing with their principals and teachers through the updated profiling and data-based monitoring and supervision.
3. Supervise schools with the least in terms of best practices and implement benchmarking activities that will serve as eye opener for some schools in the district. Adapt their school-based management best practices in terms of curriculum delivery and governance of resources, personnel, facilities and growth of their faculty members.
4. The intervention program in the form of proposed action plan should be used by the Filipino 7 teachers to enhance the level of their intellect and non-intellect skills essential in carrying-out their duties and responsibilities in monitoring and supervision.

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